

The Role of Law in Combating Noise Pollution: A Comprehensive Study in the Context of Indian Legal Framework

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Abstract

Noise pollution poses a challenge to the entire world today. India too is facing this global and harmful environmental pollution. Any form of environmental pollution directly impacts human life. Due to the general lack of seriousness regarding noise pollution, it poses a silent and invisible threat, either taking human life or causing fatal diseases. At present, there seems to be a war between human life and decibels. To combat this invisible yet dangerous problem, efforts on multiple fronts have always been necessary. Apart from technical measures, scientific measures and public awareness, this problem can also be controlled through effective implementation of legal measures. Effective legal systems have been implemented in various countries for the prevention and control of noise pollution. In India also, considering "noise pollution" as a form of air pollution, legal measures have been taken for its deterrence and control under the Environmental laws and rules. The Indian Constitution also includes provisions regarding the primacy of human life and environmental protection. Indian penal laws recognize environmental pollution as a nuisance and provide relevant penal provisions. In the present research paper, "an analytical study of Indian Constitutional and legal provisions has been presented", which have been made for the prevention and control of noise pollution.

Key words: Noise Pollution, Legislative Measures, Constitution, Penal Provisions, Environment Protection, Nuisance.

Introduction-

"Law and Society are inseparable; law reflects social values and shapes social behaviour¹"

Under the Sociological definition of law, importance is given to the "relationship between law and the society"². Law establishes social control and solves social problems through the regulation of social relations. According to Sociological jurist Roscoe Pound, "Law is a social institution to fulfil social needs"³. "The Sociological approach to Jurisprudence is based on three principles: (1) Law is a social phenomenon, (2) Analysis of legal concepts provides a partial explanation of law in action, and (3) Law is only one method of social control"⁴. The Sociological approach considers law as a social fact or reality to shape, mould and change society to sub-serve its needs, expectations and goals through law⁵. "Law is not a collection of a priori abstract rules but it is a social process of adjusting, compromising and balancing of social and individual interests"⁶. Law is a means to achieve social purposes. The function of law is to protect social purposes and suppress those personal purposes which come in conflict with them⁷.

Environmental pollution is a social problem. It adversely affects human life. By affecting human life, pollution ultimately affects society. Law plays its role in solving social problems through effective legal measures, protection of rights, determination of responsibilities, and activation of the judicial system. "Rudolf Von Ihering is considered the father of contemporary Sociological Jurisprudence"⁸. According to him, "the purpose of law is to provide uniformity to individual interests and to protect social interests". The main function of law is to maintain co-ordination by eliminating mutual conflict between individual interests and social interests⁹. Law helps in the prevention and control of social problems through the following measures: determining social norms and

standards of human behaviour, establishing effective and active mechanisms for dispute resolution, providing special protection to members of marginalized and vulnerable groups, strengthening the concept of social justice, preventing harmful acts and determining related responsibilities, establishing an effective legal system and legal framework, and empowering society through public awareness.

The law works holistically to address environmental problems. The most important work undertaken by the law in this direction is to provide legal recognition to the direct relationship between the environment and human life. Environmental standards are determined by law. The law provides effective and accurate solutions to environmental problems through the following measures: to determine and monitor the amount of environmental pollution, to make provisions for protecting natural sources, to ban the use of low-grade fuels, to regulate human behaviour in relation to the environment, to include international level provisions in state laws, to give concrete shape to the concept of environmental justice, to determine the responsibilities of different sections towards the environment, to promote the concept of “*sustainable development*”¹⁰, to determine the role and responsibilities of the Governments.

The law plays its role in preventing and controlling noise pollution by establishing an effective legal and regulatory framework, determine maximum and permissible limits of noise emissions, declaring silent zones/areas, establishing a mechanism for monitoring noise pollution, fixing accountability, coordinating various legal provisions, establishing a complaint mechanism, and punishing violations of laws and rules related to noise pollution.

Provisions of “The Constitution of India”¹¹

The Indian Constitution is included in the list of world constitutions that contain provisions relating to environment protection. The Indian Constitution mentions several provisions that ensure environmental protection. This protection is preserved in the Indian Constitution at various levels, including Preamble, Fundamental Rights¹², Directive Principles of State Policy¹³, and Fundamental Duties¹⁴.

- (a) **The Preamble**¹⁵-The Preamble, introductory part of the Constitution, is “the key to understanding the thoughts of the Constitution-makers”¹⁶; “it is a part of the Constitution”¹⁷ and it helps in understanding the objectives of the Constitution. “In the Preamble of the Constitution, the thought of social justice has been made the goal of the Constitution”¹⁸. The concept of social justice inherently includes the goal of establishing a welfare state. Social justice means equal and fair treatment of all sections and individuals of society without any discrimination, and equal access to facilities and resources for all. Environmental protection and social justice are interconnected. In the context of environmental protection, social justice means equal access to natural resources and equal benefit for all. The adverse effects of environmental pollution disproportionately affect the lower and weaker sections of society. Any form of environmental pollution challenges social justice by disproportionately affecting the poor, weak, and marginalized. To give concrete shape to “the concept of social justice”¹⁹, which finds a place in the Preamble of the Constitution, provisions related to environmental protection have been included in various Articles.
- (b) **Article 21**²⁰- “Article 21 of the Indian Constitution guarantees the right to life and personal liberty to all persons”²¹. The Indian judiciary, in its wide interpretation of “the right to life under Article 21”, has included within its ambit those rights that are not explicitly mentioned in the Constitution but are essential for the enjoyment of this right. According to the Supreme Court²², “it is not necessary for a right to be explicitly mentioned in an article of the Constitution to be considered a fundamental right; if a right is essential for the exercise of another right, then it will be considered a fundamental right even if it is not explicitly mentioned in any article of the Constitution”. The judiciary, in its interpretation of Article 21, has included “environmental protection and a pollution-free, clean and safe environment as inherent in the right to life”²³.
- (c) **Article 48-A**²⁴ – Part IV²⁵ of the Constitution outlines “*The Directive Principles of State Policy*”. These principles contain the objectives that the State is obligated to follow and incorporate into its policies in order to establish a welfare state. “Article 48-A provides that, the State shall endeavour to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard the forests and wild life of the country”²⁶. Under Article 48-A, “it is the duty of the Central and State Governments to take appropriate steps for the protection of the environment”, and “the judiciary has the authority to issue appropriate orders to ensure the fulfilment of this duty”²⁷.
- (d) **Article 51-A (g)**²⁸ – Part IV-A²⁹ was inserted in the Constitution through “The 42nd Constitutional (Amendment) Act, 1976”, which outlines certain duties to be observed by Indian citizens. Article 51-A (g) stipulates that, “It shall be the duty of every citizen of India, to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers and wild life and to have compassion for living creatures.”
- (e) **Article 253**³⁰ - Article 253 of the Indian Constitution authorizes the “Indian Parliament”³¹ to enact laws in accordance with International Conventions, Treaties, or Agreements. Article 253 provides that³², “Parliament

has power to make any law for the whole or any part of the territory of India for implementing any treaty, agreement or convention with any other country or countries or any decision made at any international conference, association or other body.” Through this provision, the Indian Parliament can implement decisions and provisions adopted at the international level for environmental protection by enacting them into law in India and can establish consistency with international provisions.

The Environment (Protection) Act, 1986³³-

This Act contains “comprehensive provisions regarding environmental protection”³⁴. The provisions of the Act authorize the Central Government to make provisions and rules for the prevention and control of noise pollution. According to clause (ii) of Section 3(2) of the Act, “the Central Government has the power to plan and implement nationwide programs for the prevention, control, and abatement of environmental pollution”³⁵. Section 6 of the Act empowers the Central Government to make rules for the regulation of environmental pollution. According to sub-section (1) of Section 6³⁶, “The Central Government may, by notification in the official Gazette, make rules in respect of all or any of the matters referred to in Section 3”. According to clause (b) of sub-section (2) of Section 6³⁷, the Central Government may make rules on the subject of, “the maximum allowable limits of concentration of various environmental pollutants (including noise) for different areas”. According to Section 25³⁸, “The Central Government may, by notification in the official Gazette, make rules for carrying out the purposes of this Act.” Section 15 of the Act, “provides for penalties in case of violation of the provisions of the Act and the rules made thereunder”³⁹.

According to Section 15(1), “such failure or contravention shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to five years or with fine which may extend to one lakh rupees or with both, and in case the failure or contravention continues, with additional fine which may extend to five thousand rupees for everyday during which such failure or contravention continues after the conviction for the first such failure or contravention”. Section 15(2) provides that “if the failure or contravention continues beyond a period of one year after the date of conviction, the offender shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to seven years”.

The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981⁴⁰-

This Act was confined only to matters relating to air pollution⁴¹. However, through the amendment Act of 1987⁴², noise pollution was involved in the definition of air pollution, thus extending the scope of this Act to noise pollution as well. According to Section 2(a)⁴³, “air pollution, means any solid, liquid or gaseous substance including noise present in the atmosphere in such concentration as may be or tend to be injurious to human beings or other living creatures or plants or property or environment”. Section 16(2)(b) of the Act casts a duty upon the “Central Pollution Control Board” to plan and cause to be executed a nation-wide programme for the prevention, control or abatement of air pollution which also includes noise pollution⁴⁴ and Section 17(1)(a)⁴⁵ casts same duty upon the “State Board”. The Central Pollution Control Board, in exercise of its power under this Act has laid down “the ambient air quality standards in respect of noise for different areas/zones”⁴⁶.

Noise Pollution is Considered a Nuisance-

“Nuisance is an unlawful interference with persons’ use or employment of land, or of some right over or in connection with it”⁴⁷. “Nuisance generally covers acts unwarranted by law which cause inconvenience or damage to the public in the exercise of rights, common to all subjects”⁴⁸. According to *Salmond*⁴⁹- “The wrong of nuisance consists in causing or allowing without lawful justification but not so as to amount trespass, if escape of any deleterious thing from his land or from elsewhere, into land in the possession of the plaintiff for example, water, smoke, smell, fumes, gas, noise, heat, vibration, electricity, disease, germs, animals, negligence.” “Nuisance is an act or omission which is an interference with or disturbance of or annoyance to a person in the exercise or enjoyment of a right belonging to him as a member of the public, when it is a public nuisance”⁵⁰.

The Judiciary has defined noise pollution as a nuisance in various cases⁵¹. Noise emitted from loudspeakers and other sources, exceeding a certain and prescribed limit, is a nuisance and is actionable. The law provides for civil and criminal remedies for nuisance. In respect of nuisance, civil remedies like injunction and compensation can be obtained through the civil court under the civil laws and criminal proceedings can be conducted under penal laws. The provisions of criminal proceedings have been incorporated in “*The Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023*”⁵² and “*The Bhartiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023*”⁵³. It is noteworthy that provisions relating to nuisance were also incorporated in the repealed criminal laws.

Action under Civil Law in Respect of Public Nuisance-

Since noise pollution is considered a public nuisance, proceedings for relief in respect of it can also be brought in a civil court. Section 91 of “*The Civil Procedure Code, 1908*” provides for the filing civil suits and obtaining

relief in respect of public nuisance as follows⁵⁴: “Section 91- Public Nuisance and other Wrongful Acts Affecting the Public- (1) In the case of a public nuisance or other wrongful act affecting, or likely to affect, the public, a suit for a declaration and injunction or for such other relief as may be appropriate in the circumstances of the case, may be instituted-

(a) by the Advocate General, or

(b) with the leave of the Court, by two or more persons, even though no special damage has been caused to such persons by reason of such public nuisance or other wrongful act.

(2) Nothing in this Section shall be deemed to limit or otherwise affect any right of suit which may exist independently of its provisions.”

Provisions regarding Public Nuisance in “The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023”⁵⁵ -

“Public nuisance” has been defined as follows in Section 270 of “The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023”⁵⁶- “270. Public Nuisance- A person is guilty of a public nuisance who does any act or is guilty of an illegal omission which causes any common injury, danger or annoyance to the public or to the people in general who dwell or occupy property in the vicinity, or which must necessarily cause injury, obstruction, danger or annoyance to persons who may have occasion to use any public right but a common nuisance is not excused on the ground that it causes some convenience or advantage.”

Section 292⁵⁷ provides for “punishment for public nuisance not otherwise punishable by the *Sanhita*, with fine which may extend to one thousand rupees”. Section 293⁵⁸ provides for “the continuation of nuisance after an injunction has been issued, or for the recurrence of such nuisance, which is punishable with simple imprisonment for a term which may extend to six months, or with fine which may extend to five thousand rupees or with both”.

Provisions regarding Public Nuisance in “The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023”⁵⁹ -

Section 152⁶⁰ of *The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023*, empowers “a District Magistrate, Sub-Divisional Magistrate, or any other Executive Magistrate specially empowered in this behalf by the State Government, to issue a conditional order for preventing or removing a nuisance”. Section 154⁶¹ provides that, “the person against whom a conditional order has been issued under Section 152 shall either comply with the said order or show cause against it”. According to Section 155⁶², “failure to comply with Section 154 renders such person liable to punishment under Section 223 of the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023*, with simple imprisonment which may extend to for a term of up to six months, or a fine of up to two thousand five hundred rupees, or both”.

The Noise Pollution (Regulation and Control) Rules, 2000⁶³-

The Central Government had made these rules for “the regulation and control of noise producing and generating sources in exercise of the powers conferred by Clause (ii) of Sub-Section (2) of Section 3, Sub-Section (1) and Clause (b) of Sub-Section (2) of Section 6 and Section 25 of the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986” read with “Rule 5 of the Environment (Protection) Rules, 1986”. The objective provision of these Rules provides that, “Whereas, the increasing ambient noise level in public places from various sources, inter-alia, industrial activity, construction activity, fire crackers, sound producing instruments, generator sets, loud speakers, public address systems, music systems, vehicular horns and other mechanical devices have deleterious effects on human health and the psychological well-being of the people; it is considered necessary to regulate and control of noise producing and generating sources with the objective of maintaining the ambient air quality standards in respect of noise.”⁶⁴

Various important provisions have been made in these Rules for the prevention and control of noise pollution:-

(1) **Clear Definition of Terms-** Rule 2 of these rules clearly defines various terms and prevents any confusion arising in this regard. Rule 2 of defines some important concepts:

Area/Zone⁶⁵; Authority⁶⁶; Educational Institution⁶⁷; Hospital⁶⁸; Person⁶⁹; Public Place⁷⁰; and Night Time⁷¹.

(2) **Authority and Responsibilities of the State Government-** “The State Government has been given the authority to classify various areas into industrial, commercial, residential and silence areas/zones for the purpose of determining and enforcing noise emission standards”⁷², further “the State Government shall take measures for abatement of noise pollution and ensure that the noise level does not exceed the standards prescribed by these Rules”⁷³.

(3) **Declaration of Silence Area/Zone-** For the purposes of the Rules, “an area of at least 100 meters around hospitals, educational institutions and courts shall be declared as silence area/zone”⁷⁴.

(4) **Responsibilities of the Authority-** “The Authority shall be responsible for the enforcement of noise pollution control measures and proper compliance with ambient air quality standards relating to noise”⁷⁵.

(5) **Regulation of Loudspeakers and Public Addressing Systems-** It is mandatory to get written permission from “the Authority for the use of loudspeakers or public addressing systems”⁷⁶, and “the use of loudspeakers

or public addressing systems at night is prohibited”⁷⁷. Furthermore, “maximum limits have been set for the amount of sound emitted by loudspeakers or public addressing systems”⁷⁸.

- (6) **Ban on the Use of Horns, Firecrackers and Sound-Emitting Construction Equipment-** “The use of horns is prohibited at night in residential areas and silence zones”⁷⁹. “Noise-emitting firecrackers will not be burst at night”⁸⁰. “The use or operation of sound-emitting construction equipment at night is prohibited in silence zones and residential areas”⁸¹.
- (7) **Penal Provisions-** Certain acts in the silence zone/area such as “singing/playing music or using sound amplifiers; beating drums; blowing horns; or beating or playing any instrument; bursting sound-emitting firecrackers; or using loudspeakers or public addressing systems, have been declared as offences and are punishable under the provisions of The Environment (Protection) Act 1986”⁸².
- (8) **Complaint to the Authority-** “Any person may make a complaint to the ‘Authority’ in case of any violation of the provisions of the Rules”⁸³ and “the ‘Authority’ shall have the power to take action on such complaint”⁸⁴.
- (9) **Determination of Ambient Quality Standards for Noise-** The Schedule of Rules prescribes maximum noise limits during “day and night” in different areas:-

“Schedule: Ambient Air Quality Standards in respect of Noise”⁸⁵

Area Code	Category of Area/Zone	Limits in dB(A) Leq	
		Day Time	Night Time
(A)	Industrial Area	75	70
(B)	Commercial Area	65	55
(C)	Residential Area	55	45
(D)	Silence Zone	50	40

Conclusion-

Law and society are interconnected. Law cannot remain untouched by the cultural and moral framework, social needs, and social problem of society. Currently, law controls and directs the behaviour of society. Pollution is a social problem. Pollution affects society by negatively impacting health and the ecosystem. The problem of pollution can be addressed through law because law establishes collective responsibility by regulating social behaviours, activities, and the determination of liabilities. The “Constitutional and legal provisions” implemented in India have played an important role in addressing and controlling the problem of noise pollution by outlining the responsibilities of the state, the rights and duties of citizens, the determination of noise emission limits, and penal provisions.

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- ¹¹ <https://share.google/YbN3TS2Rsf1N0U9vb>
- ¹² Part III, The Constitution of India
- ¹³ Part IV, Ibid
- ¹⁴ Part IV-A, Ibid
- ¹⁵ <https://share.google/tykHLGrJZF5q7iwiB>
- ¹⁶ In Re: The Berubari Union and Exchange of Enclaves, AIR 1960 SC 845
- ¹⁷ Kesavananda Bharati Sripadagalvaru and Others v. State of Kerala and Another, AIR 1973 SC 1461

- 18 <https://share.google/tykHLGrJZF5q7iwiB>
- 19 <https://share.google/qkHtNvTVTZSEM5qsA>
- 20 Ibid
- 21 "No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law."
- 22 Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India, AIR 1978 SC 597
- 23 Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar, AIR 1991 SC 420; M.C.Mehta v. Union of India, (1986) 2 SCC 176
- 24 <https://share.google/tykHLGrJZF5q7iwiB>
- 25 Article 36 to 51
- 26 Article 48-A: Protection and Improvement of Environment and Safeguarding of Forests and Wildlife
- 27 M.C.Mehta v. Union of India, (1988) 1 SCC 47
- 28 <https://share.google/tykHLGrJZF5q7iwiB>
- 29 Fundamental Duties
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- 39 Ibid
- 40 Act No. 14 of 1981
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- 42 Act No. 47 of 1987
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- 45 Ibid
- 46 Schedule of The Noise Pollution (Regulation and Control) Rules, 2000
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⁶² Ibid

⁶³ <https://share.google/IXg3Y1C1mBHF7gF7a>

⁶⁴ Ibid

⁶⁵ Rule 2(b) - "area/zone" means all areas which fall in either of the four categories given in the Schedule annexed to these rules.

⁶⁶ Rule 2(c) - "authority" means and includes any authority or officer authorized by the Central Government, or as the case may be, the State Government in accordance with the laws in force and includes a District Magistrate, Police Commissioner, or any other officer not below the rank of the Deputy Superintendent of Police designated for the maintenance of the ambient air quality standards in respect of noise under any law for the time being in force.

⁶⁷ Rule 2(e) - "educational institution" means a school, seminary, college, university, professional academies, training institutes or other educational establishment, not necessarily a chartered institution and includes not only buildings, but also all grounds necessary for the accomplishment of the full scope of educational instruction, including those things essential to mental, moral and physical development.

⁶⁸ Rule 2(f) - "hospital" means an institution for the reception and care of sick, wounded, infirm or aged persons, and includes government or private hospitals, nursing homes and clinics.

⁶⁹ Rule 2(g) - "person" shall include any company or association or body of individuals, whether incorporated or not.

⁷⁰ Rule 2(i) - "public place" means any place to which the public have access, whether as of right or not, and includes auditorium, hotels, public waiting rooms, convention centers, public offices, shopping malls, cinema halls, educational institutions, libraries, open grounds and the like which are visited by general public.

⁷¹ Rule 2(j) - "night time" means the period between 10:00 pm and 06:00 am.

⁷² Rule 3(2), The Noise Pollution (Regulation and Control) Rules, 2000, <https://share.google/IXg3Y1C1mBHF7gF7a>

⁷³ Rule 3(3), Ibid

⁷⁴ Rule 3(5), Ibid

⁷⁵ Rule 4(2), Ibid

⁷⁶ Rule 5(1), Ibid

⁷⁷ Rule 5(2), Ibid

⁷⁸ Rule 5(4), Ibid

⁷⁹ Rule 5A(1), Ibid

⁸⁰ Rule 5A(2), Ibid

⁸¹ Rule 5A(3), Ibid

⁸² Rule 6, The Noise Pollution (Regulation and Control) Rules, 2000, <https://share.google/IXg3Y1C1mBHF7gF7a>

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